

ORIGINAL ARTICLE

Influence of Surface Modification on the Vibration Characteristics of Natural Woven Banana-Jute Fiber Reinforced Hybrid Composites

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Abstract

Objectives: To analyze the vibration behavior of jute and banana fiber reinforced hybrid composites subjected to surface modification with sodium hydroxide (NaOH) and subsequent polylactic acid (PLA) coating, using both experimental method and Finite Element Analysis (FEA). **Methods:** In the present work, hybrid bio-composite laminates were developed using a hand-layup method with compression molding technique. Six different laminate configurations were prepared by varying the stacking sequence and surface modification of jute and banana mats to investigate the vibration characteristics. Experimental modal analysis and numerical simulation using ANSYS were employed to analyze the natural frequencies of the composites under various boundary conditions, including Simply Supported (SS), Clamped-Clamped (CC), and Clamped-Free (CF). The influence of ply orientation on natural frequency was also analyzed under SS and CC conditions. **Findings:** From the experimentation and FEA, it is found that chemical treatment and coating improves free vibration properties of composites due to the enhancement of interfacial bond between fiber and matrix. The hybrid composite beam BJ3 exhibited 8.89%, 21.52%, 6.48%, 21.14%, and 37.21% higher fundamental natural frequencies than BJ2, BJ1, JB3, JB2, and JB1, respectively. FEA results showed excellent predictive capability with errors consistently below 5%, suggesting that the numerical models are reliable tools for estimating the vibrational response of such hybrid composites. The study underscored the pivotal influence of ply orientation on natural frequencies, with the 0° orientation excelling in specific end conditions. **Novelty:** In this study, woven jute and banana fibers were subjected to eco-friendly surface modifications i.e. alkali (NaOH) treatment and PLA coating, which enhances fiber-matrix interfacial bonding. As a result, the developed natural fiber-reinforced composites exhibited improved mechanical performance, making them suitable for medium-strength applications in sectors i.e. automotive components, construction materials, and sustainable packaging.

Keywords: Jute and Banana Hybrid Composites; Polylactic Acid Coating; NaOH treatment; Free Vibration characteristics; Finite Element Analysis

1 Introduction

In recent years, the global emphasis on environmental sustainability has accelerated the development and application of green composite materials. Natural fiber-reinforced composites (NFRCs), particularly those based on plant fibers such as jute, banana, kenaf, and sisal, have emerged as promising alternatives to synthetic fiber composites⁽¹⁾. These natural fibers are biodegradable, renewable, lightweight, and exhibit a good balance of mechanical and acoustic properties, making them ideal for automotive, construction, and packaging applications⁽²⁾. Among biopolymers, polylactic acid (PLA) is widely used due to its biodegradability, thermal stability, and compatibility with natural fibers⁽³⁾. Though, the hydrophilic nature of natural fibers poses a challenge to achieving strong fiber–matrix adhesion, which often results in reduced mechanical performance of the composite materials⁽⁴⁾. Various studies have explored biopolymer-coated composites as sustainable materials for improving dielectric properties and electromagnetic interference (EMI) shielding effectiveness in eco-friendly applications⁽⁵⁾. Explored the use of natural fibers like jute and banana in polymer composites, highlighting their potential to enhance mechanical properties while promoting sustainability⁽⁶⁾.

The study of free vibration responses, natural frequencies, and damping characteristics offers key information into the structural integrity and suitability of composites for such engineering applications. Recent works have demonstrated that the stacking sequence, fiber orientation, surface treatments, and matrix selection significantly influence the vibrational performance of hybrid natural fiber composites. For instance, hybridization of fibers like jute, banana, and kenaf using effective stacking orders has shown improved natural frequencies and damping ratios. This research utilizes the finite element method (FEM) to analyze the free vibration behavior of hybrid jute composite beams. Experimental vibration tests were carried out on beams with cantilever boundary conditions to determine their natural frequencies⁽⁷⁾. The study further explores the effects of stacking sequence, support conditions, and ply orientation on the bending and vibrational responses of the composite beams. Through this comprehensive investigation, valuable insights are gained into the dynamic characteristics and structural performance of hybrid jute composites⁽⁸⁾.

A significant focus of current research is on the dynamic behavior of these composites, especially their free vibration and bending characteristics, which are critical for structural applications in automotive, aerospace, and packaging industries⁽⁹⁾. Finite Element Method (FEM)-based models, along with experimental modal analysis, are widely used to predict natural frequencies and assess the impact of parameters such as stacking order, fiber orientation, and end conditions⁽¹⁰⁾. Studies have demonstrated that hybrid composites fabricated using compression molding or vacuum-assisted layup methods exhibit superior vibration damping, acoustic absorption, and mechanical properties when compared to untreated or single-fiber composites. It concludes that the limitations of natural fibers have been notably mitigated, leading to enhanced properties through diverse surface modification techniques. Chemical treatments and eco-friendly approaches have proven effective in augmenting the properties of both the natural fibers and their resulting composites, albeit with certain limitations⁽¹¹⁾. This shows potential for further advancements in surface modification methodologies to unlock even greater potential in natural fiber-based materials. Vibration characteristics are notably influenced by fiber orientation and stacking sequence, leading to positive outcomes. Importantly, hybridizing composites with other fibers has significantly increased both natural frequencies⁽¹²⁾. Natural fibers are gaining attention because of their renewable nature and low environmental impact⁽¹³⁾. However, their application in composites has been hindered by their hydrophilicity and non-homogeneity in the properties. To address these issues, chemical treatments such as Sodium Hydroxide and Potassium Permanganate have been utilized⁽¹⁴⁾.

This study, a novel approach was introduced by applying a biopolymer coating of polylactic acid (PLA) following alkaline (NaOH) treatment. This dual treatment improved the surface morphology of natural fibers by removing hydroxyl groups, thereby reducing porosity and void formation. Woven jute and banana fibers underwent this eco-friendly surface treatment to enhance interfacial bonding with the polymer matrix, which in turn improved the overall performance of the resulting composites. The fabricated hybrid composite laminates show potential for medium-strength applications such as in the automotive, construction, and packaging sectors. To evaluate their dynamic behavior, both experimental and numerical analyses were carried out using ANSYS 2022 R1, focusing on how different ply orientations and boundary conditions influence the natural frequencies of the composites.

2 Methodology

2.1 Materials

In this work, reinforcing fiber materials were procured from Vruksha Composites, India, including jute woven fabric and banana woven fabric. The density of jute fiber is approximately 1200 kg/m³, while banana weave type density is around 1320 kg/m³. The matrix system employed comprises epoxy resin Bisphenol A diglycidyl ether (L12) and hardener Triethylene tetramine (K6),

sourced from Alide Engineering Services, India. The fibres were treated with a NaOH solution and coated with PLA to enhance the adhesion with fiber and matrix. Table 1 presented the comparison of woven jute and banana fibre properties.

Table 1. Material properties of natural jute and banana fiber composites

Jute fiber	Banana fiber
$E_{12} = 4.52 \text{ Gpa}$	$E_{12} = 5.83 \text{ Gpa}$
$E_{22} = 2.24 \text{ Gpa}$	$E_{22} = 4.16 \text{ Gpa}$
$\nu_{12} = 0.15$	$\nu_{12} = 0.18$
$G_{12} = 0.84 \text{ Gpa}$	$G_{12} = 0.95 \text{ Gpa}$
$\rho = 1198 \text{ Kg/m}^3$	$\rho = 1320 \text{ Kg/m}^3$

2.2 Fabrication of composite laminates

The fiber treatment process involves immersing them in a 5% NaOH solution at 30°C for 4 hours. After several washes with running water to remove NaOH residues, the fibers are submerged in a mild HCl solution. Following a final rinse with water, the fibers are dried in a 70°C hot air oven for 24 hours⁽³⁾. To coat the fibers with a 2% PLA solution, PLA particles are initially placed in a chloroform solution for 8 hours. The solution is then heated to 60°C to ensure even dispersion of Poly lactic acid. Jute and banana fibers are soaked in this solution for 5 minutes and subsequently dried in a hot air oven at 60°C for 4 hours, following 24 hours drying period at ambient temperature. In the present work, hybrid bio-composite laminates were developed using a hand-layup method with compression molding technique. Curing was performed at room temperature ($25 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$) for 24 hours under 5 bar pressure, followed by post-curing at 70°C for 4 hours. Six different laminate configurations were prepared by varying the stacking sequences and surface modifications. Figure 1 shows the stacking sequences of hybrid composites and molds used for hand-layup method. In this work, the different types of composites and their nomenclature are described in Table 2. The fabricated hybrid composite laminates for current work, as shown in Figure 2.

Fig 1. (a) Jute-Banana hybrid composite, (b) Banana-Jute hybrid composite, (c) Steel molds used for hand-layup

Fig 2. Fabricated hybrid composite laminates

Table 2. Stacking sequence of different hybrid composites

Sr. No	Composite Laminates	NaOH Treatment (wt%)	PLA coating (wt%)	Stacking sequence
1	JB1	-	-	J+B+J+B+J
2	JB2	5%	-	J+B+J+B+J
3	JB3	5%	2%	J+B+J+B+J
4	BJ1	-	-	B+J+B+J+B
5	BJ2	5%	-	B+J+B+J+B
6	BJ3	5%	2%	B+J+B+J+B

2.3 Experimental Free Vibration Test

In this work, modal analysis is carried out using the impact hammer test. The experimental setup includes an impact hammer with a sharp hardened tip (Kistler model 9722A2000) and an accelerometer affixed to the end of a rectangular composite beam (dimensions: $200 \times 20 \times 3 \text{ mm}^3$) as shown in Figure 3. This configuration is optimized to capture higher frequencies, with the hammer striking the laminate at three equally spaced points. Figure 2 shows the experimental setup for vibration analysis. While the current tests were conducted under standard laboratory conditions (25°C , 50% RH).

The accelerometer’s displacement signal is recorded on a PC through a data acquisition system (DAS) (DEWE43, Dewetron Corp., Austria) and an ICP conditioner (MSIBRACC). Two separate adapters are utilized to capture the output signals: one for the accelerometer and another for the hammer’s response upon impacting the laminate.

2.4 Finite Element Analysis

In the virtual creation of the composite plate, ANSYS software was employed in a systematic manner. The plate was designed with dimensions of $250 \times 25 \text{ mm}$ and a thickness of 3 mm, comprising five layers of fiber. The ANSYS 2022 R1 interface proved to be user-friendly for this process. The initial step involved modeling the component without specifying specific units.

Fig 3. Schematic diagram of vibration test setup

After inputting the material data, the specimen geometry was drafted using the Design Modeler and subsequently meshed in ANSYS Mechanical. The mesh size, ranging from 1 to 5 mm, was determined based on the specimen’s geometry. C3D8R elements were used to assign mesh to each section, with a global mesh size of 5 mm. Mesh sensitivity was ensured by adjusting mesh density and thickness in the plane.

Once the meshing was completed, the model was exported to ANSYS ACP-Pre^(?) for tasks such as modeling, material assignment, ply orientation, and layer stacking, as depicted in Figure 4. Each layer of the composite model was assigned unique properties, including fiber orientation and stacking sequence, resulting in a 3 mm thick solid composite model.

The meshed solid composite model was then converted to ANSYS for modal analysis using the APDL solver. Loads and boundary conditions were applied. According to the literature, boundary conditions were selected from the mechanical category’s load section. Symmetric/asymmetric/encaster options were chosen accordingly, with CC, CF, and SS boundary conditions provided for each case. CF clamped one end of the specimen, CC clamped all edges, and SS freed the U_x , U_y , R_x , and R_y of the specimen.

This study utilized the Finite Element (FE) approach to analyze the vibration behavior of a hybrid jute composite beam. It conducted research to investigate how the composite beam’s parameters responded to different loading conditions (CC, CF, and SS), while considering factors such as boundary conditions, stacking sequence and ply-orientation.

3 Results and Discussion

3.1 Experimental Vibration Analysis of Different Hybrid Composites

The natural frequency analysis of the hybrid jute-banana and banana-jute composites revealed a clear trend of performance enhancement with surface treatments as shown in Figure 4. Among the JB series, the untreated composite JB1 exhibited the lowest natural frequencies across all modes 25.27 Hz, 158.52 Hz, and 446.78 Hz for Modes 1, 2, and 3, respectively. With NaOH treatment, JB2 showed noticeable improvements, reaching 28.62 Hz, 185.84 Hz, and 523.76 Hz, highlighting enhanced stiffness

and fiber-matrix bonding. Further enhancement was observed in JB3, which was both NaOH treated, and PLA coated, achieving the highest frequencies in this series: 32.56 Hz, 216.83 Hz, and 611.11 Hz. A similar trend was evident in the BJ series. BJ1 (untreated) showed moderately higher frequencies than JB1, with values of 28.53 Hz, 192.65 Hz, and 565.43 Hz. Alkali treatment in BJ2 elevated these values to 31.84 Hz, 231.11 Hz, and 651.37 Hz. The highest overall natural frequencies were recorded in BJ3, where NaOH treatment combined with PLA coating resulted in 34.67 Hz, 311.63 Hz, and 878.31 Hz, respectively, for Modes 1, 2, and 3. Figure 5 shows the mode shapes for JB1 hybrid composite. These results demonstrate that both chemical treatment and PLA coating significantly improve the dynamic performance of natural fiber composites, with the BJ3 composite showing superior stiffness and vibrational characteristics due to optimized interfacial adhesion and reduced moisture sensitivity. NaOH treatment removes hemicellulose and lignin, increasing surface roughness and promoting mechanical interlocking. PLA coating fills surface voids, reduces hydrophilicity, and improves fiber–matrix compatibility. These chemical and physical changes reduce porosity and enhance stiffness, increase in natural frequencies, resulting in better vibrational performance.

Fig 4. Experimental Natural Frequencies (Hz) of different hybrid composites

The hybrid composite beam BJ3 exhibited 8.89%, 21.52%, 6.48%, 21.14%, and 37.21% higher fundamental natural frequencies than BJ2, BJ1, JB3, JB2, and JB1, respectively. The incorporation of treated and coated banana fibers enhanced the stiffness of the hybrid beams, indicating that reinforcing the composite with stronger fibers improves its dynamic performance. NaOH treatment removes lignin and hemicellulose, increasing fiber roughness and improving fiber-matrix interlock. PLA coating acts as a barrier to moisture and surface flaws, reducing stress concentrations and enhancing structural uniformity. Banana fiber likely has higher stiffness and lower damping than jute, contributing to better vibrational response in banana-dominant hybrids.

Fig 5. Mode shapes for JB1 hybrid composite

In addition, a comparison of mode 1 natural frequencies obtained from the present study on woven jute/banana hybrid composites with different natural fiber reinforced composite samples are given in Table 3. The data validates that the BJ3 composite from the present study achieves superior vibrational performance among jute/banana-based systems due to the applied treatments. This result also surpasses several previously reported hybrid composites like jute-banana⁽⁸⁾ (29.7 Hz) and aloe vera-jute⁽⁷⁾ (32.4 Hz), affirming the novelty and effectiveness of combining alkali treatment with PLA coating in enhancing dynamic characteristics.

Table 3. Comparison of Mode 1 Natural frequencies of different natural fiber reinforced composites

Natural fibers in composite	Mode 1 Natural frequency (HZ)	References
JB1	25.27	
JB2	28.62	
JB3	32.56	Present work
BJ1	28.53	
BJ2	31.84	
BJ3	34.67	
Jute(J)	22	
Aloe vera(A)	25	(9)
AJ	32.4	
Jute (J)	21.2	(7)
Banana(B)	27.5	(10)
JB	29.7	(8)
Bamboo	38.5	(14)

3.2 Numerical Vibration Analysis of Different Hybrid Composites

Table 4 presents the comparison between experimental and Finite Element Analysis (FEA) predicted natural frequencies for different composite beams (JB1, JB2, JB3, BJ1, BJ2, and BJ3). The results show a good agreement between experimental and numerical values, with percentage errors generally below 5% across all modes, validating the accuracy of the FEM. Moreover, the novelty of this study lies in the dual surface modification strategy that combines alkali treatment (which removes lignin and enhances surface roughness) with PLA coating (which reduces moisture absorption and improves fiber wettability). While Sohail et al.⁽⁹⁾ investigated the effect of similar treatments on natural fibers, their analysis lacked a systematic variation of stacking sequences and ply-orientations. Our study fills this gap by providing a detailed assessment of how these factors collectively influence natural frequencies under three different end conditions, validated through both experimental and finite element analysis (FEA), with errors consistently under 5%.

Table 4. Comparison of experimental and FE natural frequencies (Hz) of different hybrid composites

Composite Beams	Analysis	Natural frequency (Hz.)		
		Mode 1	Mode 2	Mode 3
JB1	Experimental	25.27	158.52	446.78
	FEM	26.35	163.84	460.23
	% Error	4.27%	3.36%	3.01%
JB2	Experimental	28.62	185.84	523.76
	FEM	29.75	190.32	536.25
	% Error	3.95%	2.41%	2.38%
JB3	Experimental	32.56	216.83	611.11
	FEM	31.25	222.45	628.12
	% Error	4.02%	2.59%	2.78%
BJ1	Experimental	28.53	192.65	565.43
	FEM	29.65	198.42	578.22
	% Error	3.93%	2.99%	2.26%
BJ2	Experimental	31.84	231.11	651.37
	FEM	33.15	238.74	667.68
	% Error	4.11%	3.30%	2.50%
BJ3	Experimental	34.67	311.63	878.31
	FEM	36.28	322.38	896.45
	% Error	4.64%	3.45%	2.07%

Table 5 presents the effect of different boundary conditions—namely simply supported (SS), clamped–clamped (CC), and clamped-free (CF)—on the natural frequencies of jute-banana hybrid composite beams. Among all, the BJ3 hybrid beam exhibits the highest natural frequencies compared to BJ2, JB3, JB2, BJ1, and JB1 beams. Under CC boundary conditions, the fundamental frequency of the BJ3 beam is higher by 4.29%, 12.15%, 8.71%, 10.12%, and 13.42% compared to BJ2, BJ1, JB3, JB2, and JB1, respectively. This improvement in frequency can be attributed to the incorporation of treated and coated banana fibers, which significantly enhances beam stiffness, thereby improving the dynamic behavior of the composite. Furthermore, it is evident that among all boundary conditions, the CF condition yields the lowest, while the CC condition results in the highest natural frequencies. This is due to the increased structural rigidity offered by the CC end constraint in the hybrid jute-banana composite beam.

3.3 Effect of ply orientation on vibration behavior

Tables 6 and Table 7 describe the effects of ply orientation on the vibration behavior of hybrid natural fiber reinforced hybrid composites under simply supported (SS) and clamped–clamped (CC) end conditions. Simulations were conducted with various ply orientations (0°, 30°, 60°, and 90°).

The banana-jute hybrid composite beam (BJ3) with a 0° ply orientation exhibits the highest natural frequencies under both clamped–clamped (CC) and simply supported (SS) boundary conditions when compared to hybrid jute composite beams with ply angles of 30°, 60°, and 90°. This superior performance is attributed to the enhanced stiffness provided by the 0° fiber

Table 5. Natural frequencies of different hybrid composites under various end conditions

End conditions	Mode	Natural Frequencies (Hz)					
		JB1	JB2	JB3	BJ1	BJ2	BJ3
SS	1	48.12	49.36	52.48	49.56	52.75	56.72
	2	274.45	294.52	322.66	304.52	358.94	415.24
	3	532.18	621.25	684.35	752.15	835.45	974.68
CC	1	62.73	64.62	65.45	63.44	68.22	71.15
	2	312.56	355.84	392.73	396.83	465.86	515.23
	3	582.78	692.64	765.42	785.74	902.15	1015.36
CF	1	26.35	29.75	31.25	29.65	33.15	36.28
	2	163.84	190.32	222.45	198.42	238.74	322.38
	3	460.23	536.25	628.12	578.22	667.68	896.45

alignment, which ensures maximum load transfer along the fiber direction. Overall, a significant influence of ply orientation on the dynamic behavior of banana-jute hybrid composite beams was evident.

Table 6. Effect on ply orientation on the natural frequencies of different hybrid composites under SS end condition

Ply-orientation	Mode	Natural frequencies (Hz)					
		JB1	JB2	JB3	BJ1	BJ2	BJ3
0°	1	48.12	49.36	52.48	49.56	52.75	56.72
	2	274.45	294.52	322.66	304.52	358.94	415.24
	3	532.18	621.25	684.35	752.15	835.45	974.68
30°	1	40.51	43.09	47.79	44.18	46.35	50.83
	2	220.33	253.24	274.37	256.16	275.93	383.54
	3	463.12	544.53	645.7	680.62	795.09	861.27
60°	1	39.62	40.59	46.67	43.18	45.42	48.25
	2	210.24	243.42	264.52	256.14	265.63	363.61
	3	453.26	524.63	614.70	667.52	775.27	841.75
90°	1	43.97	45.87	48.04	47.36	49.23	53.75
	2	260.64	265.13	296.30	305.95	336.57	385.88
	3	498.47	598.77	639.94	706.54	797.31	856.27

Table 7. Effect on ply orientation on the natural frequencies of different hybrid composites under CC end condition

Ply-orientation	Mode	Natural Frequencies (Hz)					
		JB1	JB2	JB3	BJ1	BJ2	BJ3
0°	1	62.73	64.62	65.45	63.44	68.22	71.15
	2	312.56	355.84	392.73	396.83	465.86	515.23
	3	582.78	692.64	765.42	785.74	902.15	1015.36
30°	1	56.38	58.78	59.82	59.21	63.15	67.62
	2	282.55	315.18	337.82	321.91	363.79	391.46
	3	525.64	586.56	657.43	658.52	808.25	810.93
60°	1	54.38	58.18	59.25	58.24	62.14	66.62
	2	280.55	306.18	330.88	311.97	363.59	380.46
	3	521.16	580.56	649.96	639.05	358.25	802.93
90°	1	59.45	60.76	63.94	60.03	65.35	69.65
	2	296.29	325.71	384.12	355.19	455.29	449.1
	3	501.65	602.68	722.64	673.73	831.37	896.15

4 Conclusion

This work makes a comprehensive experimental and numerical investigation into the vibrational behavior of hybrid woven jute-banana fiber reinforced polymer composites, with a special focus on the effects of eco-friendly surface modifications i.e. NaOH alkali treatment and PLA biopolymer coating. The composites were fabricated with varying stacking sequences, ply orientations and subjected to modal analysis under different boundary conditions using both experimental impact testing and Finite Element Analysis (FEA).

- The BJ3 hybrid composite laminate has 21.52% increase in natural frequency compared to BJ1, similarly JB3 hybrid composite has 28.86% increase in natural frequency compared to JB1.
- The influence of ply orientation on the natural frequencies of hybrid composite laminate was analyzed under simply supported (SS) and clamped-clamped (CC) boundary conditions. The hybrid composite beams with a 0° ply orientation exhibited significantly higher natural frequencies under both conditions, indicating superior stiffness and dynamic performance compared to other ply orientations.
- This work validates FEA based numerical analysis through close agreement with experimental results, establishing a strong correlation in predicting the natural frequencies of hybrid composite beams. The findings highlight the significant influence of ply orientation and boundary conditions on the dynamic behavior of these composites, with 0° orientations showing superior vibrational performance.
- Close correlation between experimental and numerical results (within 5% error) validates the reliability of FEA based prediction methods for such bio-composites.
- Their lightweight, biodegradable nature and improved vibrational performance make them ideal candidates for green engineering solutions in industries seeking to reduce carbon footprint.
- Integration of other natural fillers or nano-reinforcements may yield multi-functional composites with both structural and functional advantages.

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